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A Study of the Problematic State of Teachers' use of Innovation in Teaching and Learning Management at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus

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Abstract

The objectives of this research were 1) to study and compare the opinions of instructors on the problems of using innovation in teaching and learning at Thailand National Sports University, 2) to determine a policy to promote instructors to further develop learning management. A questionnaire with a rating scale of 5 levels was used as a research instrument. The reliability was at 0.821. The data were collected from a sample group consisting of 47 males and 45 females resulting a total of 92 participants. The statistics used in data analysis were mean, percentage and standard deviation. The results revealed that 1) the instructors applied the innovation in teaching and learning without sticking to traditional teaching methods (96.7 percent) and constantly developing the innovation in teaching and learning (79.4 percent). Continuous innovation (45.8%) had a small part in the application of innovation in teaching and learning management. 2) When comparing opinions classified by gender of instructors, it was found that the overall picture was not statistically significant. When considering each item, it was found that acceptance and agreeing with the use of teaching and learning innovation and planning teaching using various innovations to participate in the lesson were statistically significant differences in opinion. 3) If classified by educational qualification, the overall picture was found to be statistically significantly different. Considering each item, it was found that the development of innovation in teaching and learning regularly and continually, and the participation in the teaching and learning innovation training on a regular basis with continuity had statistically significant differences at the level of .05.

Keywords: Teaching Management, Thailand National Sports University, Problem of Innovation

1. Introduction

In terms of innovation in teaching and learning “in the past, it was often developed for student development; in other words, educational innovations for learning according to the basic learning curriculum.” (Tabuena, 2021). Therefore, according to the Office of the Secretariat of the State of Education it has been explained that the development of teachers who will be able to adopt the form of educational innovation in teaching and learning will help teachers perform their teaching and learning duties with quality. In addition to this, it can create real benefits and correspond to the needs of the students. Teachers must be encouraged to develop themselves continuously especially those who teach higher education courses. This is because it emphasizes the learning

process that considers the learner to be the most important as well as the participation of the learner in decision-making and study plan as well as evaluating their academic performance independently to create quality works and learn from authentic environments. Moreover, the learners should have direct experience in working as a group to practice emotional intelligence and work together happily. Traditional learning processes and teaching methods focus on the teacher and the content is centered. It must be adapted to suit the current context; for example, learning processes and teaching methods must be reconfigured to ensure that learners achieve their goals and meet the needs attention ability and the practical application of the learners. Therefore, the teacher and the student must work together towards the achievement of education and human development. Thus, the teacher must take the role of a supervisor and a facilitator the learning of learners in accordance with the standards of the curriculum while learners have to adjust their roles from being receivers to seekers and learn by thinking with real practice. The meaning of additional teaching innovation also refers to the advancement in computer technology and telecommunication technology in the world today (Tabuena, 2021). Therefore, educators are trying to take advantage of these technologies in the production of a large number of new teaching materials, which results in five aspects of teacher development. It reflects the competencies and characteristics of teachers that should be developed in a total of 5 aspects, namely 1) competency in teaching and learning management 2) ability to create and apply the curriculum 3) ability in information and communication technology. 4) knowledge, understanding and skills in the learning management assessment process, and 5) teachers had a change in working behavior within themselves and among their peers.

Therefore, the results that the researchers aimed to develop in teachers were the most common. The development of teaching and learning management competency of teachers, which consists of having skills in organizing learning activities, managing teaching and learning systematically and efficiently and be able to evaluate the development and learning of learners.

The second most effective goal is the development for teachers to change working behavior within themselves and between fellow teachers. It is the general behavior of teachers. However, it will directly and indirectly affect the quality of learning management and student development. This may cause problems in teaching and learning in Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri campus. These problems included 1) teachers use teaching innovations that are inconsistent with the age of the learners, 2) teachers do not develop further innovations in learning management by sticking to the original method, and 3) teachers do not exchange techniques and learning management methods. This lead the researcher to be interested in confirming such a situation as information and applying the results of the research in conjunction with policy formulation of the university's educational management development for learners to be more effective.

2. Objectives

1. To study the level of problems toward the use of teaching and learning innovations in Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus.
2. To study and compare the opinions of instructors on the problems of using innovation in teaching and learning management of the Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus classified by gender and level.

Quantitative research method (survey) was utilized using a questionnaire as a tool for data collection. The details are as follows.

3. Population and sample group

The population consisted of 150 teaching staff at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus. The sample group was selected by using accidental sampling method. Thus, the sample group was comprised of 92 respondents. The number of the sample group was determined by (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970)

4. Research Instrument

The instrument used in this research was a questionnaire with a 5-level rating scale created by the researchers based on academic principles and theories on the use of educational innovation. The aim of the questionnaire was to identify the problems of using innovation in teaching and learning among the instructors of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus. The questionnaire was divided into 3 main components which were 1. Teacher factor 2. Factors promoting innovation in teaching and learning management and 3. The learner factor. Thus, the questionnaire consisted of a total of 30 questions.

5. Validity and Reliability

The researchers validated the research instrument by using 5 experts in the field of education and research measurement. After that the Index of Item objective Congruence (IOC) was calculated. Only the items with the IOC at .06 or higher selected. After that the reliability of instrument was examined. The questionnaire was tried out with 30 instructors from another university with similar characteristics to the sample group. Cornbrash's Alpha Confident was used to determine the reliability at the level of 0.7-1.00 [3]. It was found that the reliability of the instrument used in the study was at 0.821.

6. Research Procedures

1. The questionnaire was prepared for inquiring and interviewing. After that, it was validated by using IOC.
2. The data were collected at Thailand National Sports University, Chon Buri Campus.
3. The sample group was selected by accidental sampling method. They were informed regarding the objectives of the study together with the date, time and location for data collection. Also, the participants were briefed on the procedures. Finally, they were asked to sign a consent form.
4. The data were collected as planned.
5. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted.

7. Data Analysis

The data were analyzed based using a computer program. The statistics consisted of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Independent T – Test was employed in order to compare the opinions of the instructors of Thailand National Sports University on the problems when using educational innovations in their class. The criteria used for data interpretation was Likert Scale.

8. Findings

According to the general information of the instructors expressing their opinions on the problematic use of teaching and learning innovations of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus, it was found that was 51.1 percent of the respondents were male while 48.9 percent of the respondents were female. The majority of the respondents (80.4%) acquired graduate degrees. Only 19.6 percent had a bachelor's degree

Table 1: The Opinions of the Instructors on the Problematic Use of Teaching and Learning Innovations of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus in the Aspect of Instructor

Description	Level of Opinion		
	Mean	SD.	Interpretation
1. The teaching and learning innovation is suitable for the age of the students.	3.87	.73	High
2. The instructors always develop their teaching innovation.	3.93	.69	High
3. The instructors also further develop their teaching innovation continuously.	3.77	.77	High

4. The instructors accept and agree to implement teaching innovation.	4.53	.56	Highest
5. The instructors are not stick to traditional teaching method.	4.34	.70	High
6. The instructors always participate in training related to teaching and learning innovation.	3.50	.67	Moderate
7. The instructors continuously participate in training related to teaching and learning innovation.	3.53	.71	High
8. The instructors exchange knowledge regarding teaching and learning innovation.	3.74	.82	High
9. The instructors include the use of teaching and learning innovation in their lesson plans	4.03	.80	High
10. The instructors are fond of using teaching and learning innovation.	3.93	1.03	High
Total	3.91	.75	High

According to Table 1, it shows the results of the survey of instructor' opinions on the problematic use of teaching and learning innovations of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus, it was found that in most cases, instructors used innovation in teaching and learning. They did not stick with the traditional teaching method. This was in the highest level of opinion.

It was accounted for 86.9%. Secondly, the instructors were consistently developed and furthered innovation in teaching and learning management with the highest level of opinion (79.4%). It shows that teachers placed importance on continually developing innovations in teaching and learning. Furthermore, they participated in the continuous training on teaching and learning in innovation at the highest level of opinion (46.8%). It shows that less than half of the total number of instructors agreed that continual participation in teaching and learning innovation training is less important in bringing innovation to teaching.

Table 2: The Opinions of the Instructors on the Problematic Use of Teaching and Learning Innovations of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus in the Aspect of Promoting Educational Innovation

Description	Level of Opinion		
	Mean	SD.	Interpretation
1. The university has set a clear and concrete policy for educational innovation.	2.84	.684	Moderate
2. The university provides training to equip teachers with the knowledge of continuing education innovation management.	2.78	.810	Moderate
3. The university encourages personnel to create innovation for reaching materials annually.	2.75	.872	Moderate
4. The university allocates a budget for creating other materials for teachers.	2.03	.907	Low
5. The university provides various materials for teachers to choose from.	2.01	.734	Low
6. The university organizes a conference on managing innovation in education, introducing new innovations for teachers to continue to use in the classroom.	2.33	.866	Low
7. The university organizes meetings using all teachers to produce innovations and exchange presentations.	2.05	.717	Low
8. The university has installed computer and internet networks as well as equipment to support innovative educational media in the classroom.	2.92	.929	Moderate
9. The university has a plan to develop an educational curriculum related to educational innovation.	2.53	.907	Moderate
10. The university regularly invites lecturers to train and educate staff in order to encourage teachers to always learn and develop innovation.	2.39	.851	Low
Total	1.42	1.50	Low

According to Table 2, it shows the results of the opinion of instructors on the problematic state of using innovation in teaching and learning in terms of promoting innovation in teaching and learning of Thailand National Sports

University, Chon Buri Campus. The results demonstrated that most of the instructors expressed their opinions about the support and promotion of teaching and learning innovation from the university as in moderate to low level. The topics that had a low average were that the university provides various materials for teachers to choose from with the mean of 2.01. Moreover, budget allocation for making media for teachers was in the low level with the mean of 2.05. In addition to this, on the topic stating that the university organizes a conference on managing innovation in education, introducing new innovations for teachers to continue to use in the classroom was in the low level with the mean of 2.05. Further, on the topic stating that the university regularly invites lecturers to train and educate staff in order to encourage teachers to always learn and develop innovation was with the mean of 2.39. It shows that the instructors were interested in getting more support in innovation in teaching and learning at Thailand National Sports University, Chon Buri campus especially in terms of budget and training on new teaching innovations continuously.

An overview of instructors' opinions towards the use of innovations in teaching and learning management in terms of students of Thailand National Sports University, Chon Buri Campus was at a moderate level. Programs related to creating positive attitudes for students to work in teams affecting the effectiveness of educational innovation initiatives in each class were at a good level.

Table 3: The Comparison of the Opinions of the Instructors on the Problematic Use of Teaching and Learning Innovations of Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus Classified by the Genders of the Instructors (n=92)

Description	Male (n=47)		Female (n=45)		t	Sig.
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Instructors	3.89	.54	3.94	.38	-.56	.58
The Promotion of Teaching Innovation	2.57	.87	2.35	.76	1.27	.98
Learners	2.97	2.35	2.92	.92	.27	.72
Total	3.14	1.25	3.07	.68	.32	.76

* was statistically significant at the level of .05

The results from the comparison of the opinions of the instructors on the problematic use of teaching and learning innovations of Thailand national sports university chon buri campus classified by the genders of the instructors demonstrated that overall, the opinions of the instructors were not different with any statistical significance at the level of 05. It was found that the opinions of instructors on the promotion of teaching and learning innovation in terms of installation of computer networks and Internet networks, including equipment to support innovative educational media in the classroom and the educational curriculum development plan concerning the provision of educational innovation had different opinions at the statistically significant level .05. According to the results of comparing the opinions of instructors toward the use of innovation in learning and teaching management of students of Thailand National Sports University, Chon Buri Campus classified by instructor's educational background, it was found that overall there was a statistically insignificant difference at the .05 level and when considering items, it was found that there was a statistically insignificant difference at the .05 level.

9. Discussion

The study on “The Problematic State of Using Innovation in Teaching and Learning at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus” aimed to identify the problematic state of using innovation in teaching and learning at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus. It can be discussed as follows:

According to the objective to identify the problematic state of using innovation in teaching and learning at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus, there are three factors related to this issue. The three factors are instructors, teaching and learning innovation and learners.

1. Based on the aspect of the instructors, the results indicate that the instructors are insufficiently trained and developed on teaching innovation. Therefore, there should be training to learn how to use innovations such as

training on the production of new teaching materials, production of teaching materials to meet the needs of learners at different levels and the use of sustainable teaching innovations. This in line with Tabuena (2021) who concluded that building teachers' attitudes and skills related to educational innovation management will help support teaching and learning for learners to have knowledge and understanding faster because it improves skills. The instructor lack of information exchange between different learning groups causing problems in the integration of teaching and learning management that is quite difficult. Hence, when assessing outside the university, the assessment results were at a moderate level. Jana and Megan (2020) studied and examined the solutions to develop learner skills by exchanging learning skills in teaching and learning management of teachers. Therefore, every subject group should be encouraged to exchange information, discuss, suggest, integrate knowledge together in order to create a joint modern innovation, which is in line with the research on "Studies of Educational Innovation Management Approaches for Teaching and Research Development of Teachers" (Tabuena, 2021). It can be concluded that the steps to promote the management of educational innovation are most effective and beneficial. There must be a presentation stage to exchange knowledge and help each other between teachers or academic presentation stage and push for a policy to promote the use of innovation in the classroom or classroom innovation promotes. Administrators should pay attention in managing educational innovations and collaborate with teaching staff to understand the reasons and benefits of innovation and research. Research work and educational innovation should be considered to promote cooperation between the teaching staff to work together more (Singgram and Thanaiudompat, 2023).

Based on the aspect of teaching and learning innovation, the results showed that at Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus, there is a shortage of equipment used to produce modern innovations and they are not in practical conditions such as television sets, loudspeakers, and computer connection cables. In addition, Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus do not have an internet system and a wifi system that covers all classrooms. The equipment facilitating the use of innovation in teaching and learning that is out of date which equipment is conducive facilitating the use of innovation in the classroom. It was damaged due to uneven maintenance, probably because of the budget allocated to Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri campus. The equipment is not enough to meet the need for learning management innovation. According to (Tabuena, 2021), Jana and Megan (2020) who conducted a study on the problems and needs of managing an English class for learning disabilities in grades 2-3 and a study on educational innovation management approaches for use in teaching and research development of teachers, it can be concluded that university administrators must provide financial support. The budget for the purchase of media equipment is appropriate and sufficient for supervision. Regularly following up and recommending instructional management for students in learning should be implemented. Moreover, promoting and supporting equipment and technology including modern and appropriate information systems in each classroom is an important way to promote management of the use of innovation for education as well. This is also in line with Jana and Megan (2020) who studied that the development of teaching and learning innovation needs for the development of media and technology. It can be seen that the university needs to develop media and technology in educational institutions to meet the needs of teachers to support the use of educational innovation more efficiently.

It can be concluded that the university should allocate a budget for innovation in teaching and learning and recruit modern computers ready for use in the classroom. This can promote and support the teaching and learning style by using innovation to provide quality teaching and cause maximum efficiency for learners, including organizing training for teachers on developing and using management innovations. Continuous teaching and formulating a curriculum development plan on the use of teaching and learning innovations for teachers including encouraging teachers to have a positive attitude about teaching and learning innovation for students in the class by conducting a meeting to exchange the use of teaching innovation between learning groups and increase motivation about implementing teaching innovation by rewarding should be implemented (Thanaiudompat, 2023).

2. Based on the aspect of students, due to the system of Thailand National Sports University, Chon Buri Campus, students who are athletes are allowed to participate in online class. Many of the respondents suggested that there should be an e – learning platform to support this group of students. This is because the athlete students are usually to practice and train. Unable to attend the class might cause a negative result in their academic performance.

10. Recommendation

Recommendation for Implementing the Research Results

1. All departments of the university administrators are important people in promoting and listening to problems that arise in the process of creating educational innovation in the university. Universities should allocate budgets for innovation in teaching and learning and provide modern computers ready for use in the classroom. This should be done in order to promote and support the teaching and learning style by using innovations to provide quality teaching and learning for maximum efficiency to the students.
2. Encouraging teachers to change their attitudes is important to initiate initiatives to encourage teachers to have attitudes and feelings to understand the importance of using innovations in education and to want to change their own traditional teaching behavior. The practice initiating the use of various innovations should be in line with the needs of the students in the current situation with rapid changes in technology and various social conditions in the classroom. Building a model teaching team based on experience that effectively implements instructional innovations is another important factor in encouraging teachers to develop more teaching innovations. Moreover, the model educator can give educators good advice on creating interesting and effective innovations, making educators have a better attitude and understanding of the importance of using innovations for education than before.
3. Besides promoting the above aspects, the cooperation in creating educational innovations between teachers who teach together may include preparing a curriculum development plan for creating educational innovations, providing various experimental materials for teachers to choose from, organizing meetings about managing new innovations in education by introducing new innovations for teachers to use in the classroom. Furthermore, organizing meetings to produce innovations and share presentations should be conducted together with supervision and follow-up of instructors regularly to inspect and evaluate teaching. This should include the use of innovations in education. Teaching management can be another way that can encourage teachers to develop innovations in education to create a quality classroom between teachers and students effectively.

11. Recommendation for Future Research

In order to conduct more in-depth in the study of problem-solving on the use of educational innovations, the researcher should study the relationship in each sample group that is different in the subject, educational background, learning subject groups, ages and subjects responsible for teaching in different parts.

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